

THE OLDEST CUSTOMS IN MANKIND

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7874502>

Abstract

Folk traditions were created on the basis of social and spiritual needs of ethnic groups in the course of long historical development, on the basis of their intellectual and creative activity, environment, nature, It is a priceless social and cultural heritage that embodies dreams, experiences, achievements and other values, passed from generation to generation depending on the labor process. This is the legacy of formation We will try to find answers to such questions as when it started and what it looks like through this article. Ancient beliefs and traditions are the first results of people's efforts to understand the secrets of nature, life, and livelihood. In primitive times, different beliefs developed and mixed with each other. As a result of the combination of different concepts and beliefs *Polytheism* formed. Holidays and ceremonies were formed and developed under the influence of this. That is *Animistic, fetishistic, totemistic* unique traditions appeared under the ideas. The fact that beliefs did not meet the requirements of the times as people's needs, consciousness, and thinking changed, as life progressed, remained in the depths of history, some of them changed along with time, some of them discovered new content in different forms and were preserved during long historical processes.

Keywords: Primitive people, gang, skill, habit, "polygamy", Hole Cave, Animism, polytheism, ancient beliefs

INTRODUCTION

The oldest beliefs and traditions are the first results of people's efforts to understand the secrets of nature, life, and livelihood. The fact that beliefs did not meet the requirements of the times as human needs, mind, and thinking changed, as life progressed, remained in the depths of history. While studying a topic, the researcher must determine its starting point, i.e. its root, and reach its essence. Therefore, we will start studying traditions, customs and values from the oldest ones. We are talking about the customs related to the life of primitive people. It is known that in the most ancient times, people lived in groups. This helped them fight against wild animals, natural disasters, and avoid the cold. Each gang had its own leader. Over time, the leaders began to introduce certain privileges for themselves. This increased the number of contenders for leadership in the gang. This led to frequent disagreements between the claimants and the leading leader. Often these conflicts led to bloodshed and fighting. Special battles took place between the leader of the gang and the claimants. Sometimes these fights became a big spectacle for gang members. The defeated in battle were often killed to prevent them from claiming leadership again. Ghalib was the leader of the gang. In order to put an end to such bloodshed and chaos, as well as to regulate relations within the clan, customs that serve the common good of the members of the society were introduced in the primitive

community system. Habits such as unconditional obedience to the leader, sharing the things obtained by hunting or gathering together, and punishing those who started quarrels in the community have appeared since primitive times. During these times, custom also performed the function of law. Everything in nature appears out of necessity. The world of plants, the entire living world and the “master of all creation – man” also came into existence based on vital necessity. Among all creatures, man’s desire to live well is so strong that he evolved rapidly. A good life is achieved as a result of hard work, struggle, and overcoming difficulties. The need to strive for a good life requires constant training of the mind and conscious work. Conscious work creates experience – skills. Conscious work and experience keeps everything from “inventing” anew. The use of work experience by others is the basis for development. Experiences created on the basis of conscious work gradually turn into skills and habits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The deeper one goes into the distant past, the more difficult it is to study it. Because it is difficult to find sources for its research. Nevertheless, it is necessary to study the history of our ancestors in depth, using existing information and looking for new sources, logically analyzing them. Otherwise, historical consciousness cannot be restored. History is our foundation. In order to gain strength from this support, it is necessary to know it well. The more we appreciate our history, the brighter our future will be. In this work, we want to study the customs of our ancient ancestors as an important part of our ancient culture.

In history, the ratio of men and women has not always been equal. Sometimes the number of men increased, other times the number of women increased. This was the basis for the formation of specific customs. It is known to us that there were customs of polygamy in history. However, in ancient times there was also its opposite - polygamy. In particular, the famous archaeologist N. Tolstov gives interesting information about polygamy in his work "Ancient Khorezm". When studying the ancient customs of primitive people, one can find more information about their death than about birth and growth. Because by studying the cemeteries that have been preserved since ancient times, you can get an idea about the burial habits of the people of that time. Burying a person after death is one of the oldest customs. Based on the study of the graves of people who lived in the Selungur cave, Kolbuluq area, and Teshiktash cave, it is possible to gain a certain understanding of the habits of primitive people. Some of the habits of primitive people are difficult to understand now. For example, in ancient times, customs such as killing the infirm, taking the elderly to foreign places, feeding the corpses to dogs and birds, collecting the bones of the deceased and putting them in an ossuary, making utensils from the skin of the enemy, and making dishes from the skull are known from history. Along with such difficult to understand customs, there are also many examples that can be learned from the history. In particular, the customs of our ancestors, such as courage, bravery, patriotism, fear of death, are still considered a positive phenomenon. Roman historian Quintus Cursi Rufus, who lived in the 1st century, wrote that when they tried to execute the Sogdians, they behaved cheerfully and bravely, and admired the invaders.

It is known that in Central Asia, spring, summer and autumn provide favorable conditions for raising cattle. In winter, it is difficult to feed cattle. Therefore, in ancient times, many livestock were slaughtered in the fall and stored as meat for winter consumption. In winter, there were dozens of special processing methods, such as meat storage, drying, salting, grilling, etc. The

process of preparing meat for the winter took place in the form of a large gathering - hashar and feast. This custom was later called "Sag'im".

In general, in the process of historical development, customs play a very important role in mankind's step from wildness to civilization. Starting from the primitive society, in the process of the development of relations between people, the system of order, customs and ceremonies directly related to the life of a person, family, and society begins to form. These customs and rituals had a great impact on the development of a person, family and community.

RESULTS

As people's life experience increased, they sought to understand the mysteries of nature more deeply. In addition to understanding natural phenomena with the mind, they also tried to feel with the heart. In this way, concepts began to appear in people's minds and beliefs in their hearts. Clear, convincing concepts and beliefs have been combined and perfected. Since the end of the Paleolithic period in primitive society, as a result of people's desire to understand and feel the surrounding phenomena, various concepts and beliefs, including fetishistic - believing in the power of material things, totemistic - worshiping the divine power of animals and plants, animistic - believing in divine powers in the form of soul and spirit, polytheistic - polytheism, worship of the sun, earth, water, fire, etc. began to appear. Of course, these beliefs were manifested in harmony with the natural climatic conditions of each place. For example, one of the widespread religious ideas in Central Asia is Animism. This concept was introduced into science by the English ethnologist E. Tyler as the first stage of religion. Animism means the worship of souls and spirits. Deifying the spirits of deceased ancestors, worshiping the souls of living people, illuminating the image of the forces of nature and worshiping their spirits is an animistic view. According to animistic views, after a person dies, his soul separates from his body and lives as an invisible spirit. Therefore, along with the deceased, food, ornaments, wealth, and clothes are also buried in the grave. Ancient peoples with strong animistic beliefs buried their wives, pets, and household goods along with the deceased. For example, when a grave dating back to the 2nd millennium BC was opened in Sopollitepa, various dishes - trays, jugs, mirrors, decorations - jewelry, animal bones were found. This indicates that animistic views and traditions existed in our country even before 4th thousand years ago. Some of them have remained in the depths of history, some have been improved and have reached the present day. One such animistic ritual is the offering of sacrifices to the spirits of deceased ancestors.

DISCUSSION

As we delve deeper into this topic, we will discover what we can discover and how useful these things will be to us. Just like the starting point of everything in the world, there is a common basis for our customs and values related to our current lifestyle. A path of long years of experience has been covered and learning from it will only benefit everyone. Since ancient times, spiritual growth - development, which arose on the basis of the natural needs of people, encouraged them to move, work, fight. This led to the growth of their consciousness, faith and spirituality. Effective experiences have been formed based on the conscious work of people. Deeply meaningful and culturally shaped experiences have become habits. Rituals appeared on the basis of customs that gained importance. Holidays are formed on the basis of events that have a special place in the life of the community and joyful events. Experiences and habits related to conscious work are of special importance in the spiritual life of people. Traditions

associated with the oldest activities, including gathering customs (natural food-gathering experiments, competitive games), hunting games (pre-hunting training - games, the last ceremony after the hunt, spectacle games), animal husbandry activities (hunting and training wild animals, habits of caring for domestic animals, preparing meat for the winter), farming habits (planting crops in spring, harvesting in autumn), advanced work experiences, labor achievements, the example of the elderly, created an opportunity to effectively use the heritage of ancestors. Customs related to the labor process, along with the prosperity and decoration of life, played an important role in the development of many types of culture, including games, spectacles, pantomime, dance, and musical arts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I can say that the concepts of people and holiday are closely related. Because in all times, the people spent some day of the year with joy. Since ancient times, people have shown their happiness and dreams on holidays. They believed that holidays provide a convenient opportunity to ask God for wishes related to fate and sustenance on such days. Ancient beliefs and traditions are the first results of people's efforts to understand the secrets of nature, life, and livelihood. The fact that beliefs did not meet the requirements of the times as human needs, consciousness changed, and life progressed remained in the depths of history, some of them changed along with time, some of them discovered new content in various forms and were preserved during long historical processes. The most ancient traditions of human life, including group living rituals, leadership rites, initiation rites, various burial customs, sacrificial rites, orgistic celebrations, and the foundations of family and wedding rites. polygamous, exogamous, monogamous habits played a significant role in the development of the primitive community. They were of great importance in preserving and increasing the experiences and achievements of primitive people.

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